

A Study of Leadership Perspectives in Bharath Earth Movers Limited (BEML)

Dr. G. Haranath

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Yogi Vemana University, Kadapa (India)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 March 2019

Keywords

Socio, Economic, public sector.

ABSTRACT

This paper attempts to study the perspectives of leadership relating to positivism and negativism and relationship of leadership with Socio Economic and Organization Position (SEOP) variables, in a public-sector enterprise, Bharath Earth Movers Limited (BEML). The analysis of leadership perspectives reveals that on the composition of characteristic features positivism is apparent over negativism.

1. Introduction

The practice of leadership has been understood in many ways. As a result it is viewed from the extremes in different degrees like autocratic and democratic; boss-centered and employee-centered; concern for people and concern for production etc. However, all these behavioural patterns are adjudged keeping in view of the purposes of leadership. The approaches adopted so far could not focus on the positivism and negativism of leaders. In the world literature, there are both great leaders among many good and bad leaders. The greatness of a leader is assessed from his effectiveness in achieving the avowed objectives but the qualities of good and bad of leaders are evaluated on the basis of their approaches while transacting with others. More than historical school, the Puranic School has emphasised the characteristics, especially of leaders in terms of divine (good) and diabolic (bad). In the Bhagavad-Gita in chapter 16, the divine characteristics are mentioned covering fearlessness, purity, devotion, charity, sacrifice, austerity, uprightness, reverence for scriptures, a desire for universal welfare and a will to surrender their will to God not the divine natures, ... The bad qualities (the opposite of the above) are listed as hypocrisy, arrogance, self-conceit, wrath, a disregard for other people's rights and happiness, and ignorance of scriptures mark the diabolic nature... In order to understand perspectives of leadership relating to positivism and negativism among the staff of BEML, a schedule is constructed and used.

At present the success and failure of organizations are attributed to the effectiveness of leaders in the organizational setting. Thus, leadership has become indispensable and managers are to be replaced by leaders, despite the argument that leadership is dispensable by another school of thought. As such, the topic of leadership has occasioned research studies without limit, and new dimensions are added to leadership theory and practice. What is the impact of different behavioural patterns of leaders? The present empirical research study of Bharath Earth Movers Limited (BEML) addresses itself to this issue.

2. Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To study the relationship of Leadership Perspectives with certain Socio Economic and Organizational Position (SEOP) variables of employees in BEML;
2. To study the relationship between Leadership Perspectives of employees in BEML; and
3. To find out the differences in Leadership Perspectives in BEML.

The hypotheses formulated for the study are the following:

1. There is no significant relationship between Leadership Perspectives and the SEOP variables of employees in BEML.
2. There is no significant relationship between Leadership Perspectives of employees in BEML.
3. There is no significant difference between the different Leadership Perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML.

3. Research Methodology

The study is mainly based on primary data collected from the employees of BEML, K.G.F.-Kolar Gold Fields (Kolar District, Karnataka) which are categorized as workers, supervisors and officers. For the present study only the officers are taken into consideration, the officers are in several Grades, from Grade-I to Grade-XII in the rising order of seniority in the hierarchy, i.e. from Assistant Engineers to Chairman and Managing Director. However for the present inquiry, officers from Grade-I to Grade-VII only are taken into consideration viz., Deputy General Manager (DGM), Assistant General Manager (AGM), Senior Manager (SM), Managers (M), Assistant Managers (AM), Engineers (E) and Assistant Engineers (AE).

From each grade of officers 50 per cent are drawn as the sample. The number of samples drawn from each grade is listed below. The total sample for the study consists of 399 out of 784 officers.

In the present study, two schedules were used to collect the data: Schedule-I and Schedule-II. Schedule-I was designed to elicit the information relating to the SEOP variables viz., designation, age, length of service, education and economic status.

Schedule-II was used to measure Leadership Perspectives consisting of 40 items relating to Positive Leadership (S) and Negative Leadership (G). This is divided into two parts viz., Part-A and Part-B. Part-A covering 20 items relating to Positive Leadership and Part-B covering 20 items relating to Negative Leadership. In this schedule the respondents were asked to respond on a five point scale comprising the categories of (a) Strongly Agree (5), (B) Agree (4), (C) Moderately Agree (3), (D) Disagree (2) and (E) Strongly Disagree (1).

The data collected through the schedules were processed and the results tested with the hypotheses by employing appropriate statistical tools like mean, S.D., 't' values and correlation.

The correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives were computed. Following this, correlations were computed between leadership perspectives viz., positive and negative leadership styles. With a view to find out difference between the five pairs viz., DGMs and AGMs; AGMs and SMs; SMs and Ms; Ms and AMs; AMs and Es of BEML in positive

and negative leadership styles, mean, standard deviation (S.D.) were computed. Further, with an intent to find out significant difference between the five pairs 't' test was computed.

4. Analysis of the study

The presentation and discussion of the data pertains to the following:

- I. Relationship of SEOP variables with leadership perspectives for officers of BEML viz., DGM, AGM, SM, M, AM and E.
- II. Inter-correlation of leadership perspectives for officers of BEML.
- III. The difference between leadership perspectives at inter levels of officers of BEML.

I. Relationship of SEOP Variables with Leadership Perspectives

Table 1

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of DGMs (N=8)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	0.145	-0.635
2	Age	-0.320	-0.435
3	Experience	0.216	-0.700
4	Education	0.460	-0.389
5	Economic Status	0.383	0.204

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 1 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables viz., designation, age, experience, education and economic status, and leadership perspectives viz., positive and negative leadership styles of DGMs of BEML. None of the

SEOP variables were found not to be significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 2

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of AGMs (N=16)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	0.183	-0.323
2	Age	-0.118	*0.579
3	Experience	-0.471	0.440
4	Education	0.093	-0.292
5	Economic Status	-0.004	-0.147

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 2 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives of AGMs of BEML. 'age' was significantly and positively correlated with 'negative leadership' style ($r=0.579$, $P<0.05$) indicating that 'negative leadership' style increases with the increase of 'age'. None of the other SEOP variables, however, were found not to be

significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is rejected in the case of 'age' vs 'negative leadership' style, and is accepted in all other cases.

Table 3

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of SMs (N=24)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	**0.547	0.127
2	Age	*-0.429	0.070
3	Experience	-0.207	-0.065
4	Education	0.324	0.060
5	Economic Status	0.174	-0.270

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 3 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives of SMs of BEML. 'Designation' was significantly and positively correlated with 'positive leadership' style ($r=0.547$, $P<0.01$) indicating that 'positive leadership' style increases with the increase of 'designation'. The correlation between 'age' and 'positive leadership' style was found to be significantly negative ($r= -0.429$, $P<0.05$) indicating that the 'positive leadership' style

decreases with the increase of 'age'. None of the other SEOP variables, however, were found not to be significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is rejected in the case of 'designation' vs 'positive leadership' style and 'age' vs 'positive leadership' style, and is accepted in all other cases.

Table 4

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of Ms (N=48)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	-0.059	0.187
2	Age	-0.057	0.236
3	Experience	-0.055	0.276
4	Education	0.183	-0.107
5	Economic Status	*0.316	0.030

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 4 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives of Ms of BEML. 'economic status' was significantly and positively correlated with 'positive leadership' style ($r=0.316$, $P<0.05$) indicating that 'positive leadership' style increases with the increase of 'economic status'. None of the other SEOP variables,

however, were found not to be significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is rejected in the case of 'economic status' vs 'positive leadership' style, and is accepted in all other cases.

Table 5

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of AMs (N=88)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	0.018	-0.038
2	Age	0.028	0.032
3	Experience	0.114	-0.008
4	Education	0.146	0.068
5	Economic Status	-0.037	0.109

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 5 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives of AMs of BEML. None of the SEOP variables were found not to be significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the

hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 6

Inter-correlation between SEOP variables and Leadership perspectives of Es (N=118)

S.No	SEOP Variables	Leadership Perspectives	
		Positive leadership	Negative leadership
1	Designation	-0.010	-0.028
2	Age	** -0.284	-0.068
3	Experience	** -0.268	0.0153
4	Education	-0.008	-0.175
5	Economic Status	* -0.220	-0.122

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 6 presents the inter-correlation between SEOP variables and leadership perspectives of Es of BEML. The correlation between 'age' and 'positive leadership' style was found to be significantly negative ($r = -0.284$, $P < 0.01$) indicating that the 'positive leadership' style decreases with the increase of 'age'. 'experience' was also significantly but negatively correlated with 'positive leadership' style ($r = -0.268$, $P < 0.01$) indicating that 'positive leadership' style decreases with the increase of 'experience'. 'economic status' was significantly but negatively correlated with 'positive leadership' style ($r = -$

0.220, $P < 0.05$) indicating that 'positive leadership' style decreases with the increase of 'economic status'. None of the other SEOP variables, however, were found not to be significantly correlated with leadership perspectives. Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives and SEOP variables of employees in BEML" is rejected in the case of 'age' vs 'positive leadership' style, 'experience' vs 'positive leadership' style and 'economic status' vs 'positive leadership' style, and is accepted in all other cases.

II. Inter-Correlation of Leadership Perspectives

Table 7

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of DGMs (N=8)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		-0.406
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 7 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of DGMs of BEML. The leadership perspectives were found not to be significantly correlated between them.

Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 8

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of AGMs (N=16)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		-0.281
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 8 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of AGMs of BEML. The leadership perspectives were found not to be significantly correlated between them.

Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 9

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of SMs (N=24)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		0.249
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 9 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of SMs of BEML. The leadership perspectives were found not to be significantly correlated between them.

Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 10

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of Managers (N=48)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		0.228
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 10 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of Managers of BEML. None of the leadership perspectives were found not to be significantly

correlated between them. Hence, the hypothesis of “there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML” is accepted.

Table 11

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of AMs(N=88)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		0.135
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 11 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of AMs of BEML. None of the leadership perspectives were found not to be significantly

correlated between them. Hence, the hypothesis of “there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML” is accepted.

Table 12

Inter-correlation of Leadership Perspectives of Engineers (N=118)

Leadership Perspectives	Positive Leadership	Negative Leadership
Positive leadership		**0.480
Negative leadership		

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 12 presents the inter-correlations between leadership perspectives of Engineers of BEML. The ‘positive leadership’ style was correlated significantly and positively with ‘negative leadership’ style ($r= 0.480$, $P< 0.01$) indicating that

‘negative leadership’ style increases with the increase of ‘positive leadership’ style. Hence, the hypothesis of “there is no significant relationship between leadership perspectives of employees in BEML” is rejected.

III. The Difference between Leadership Perspectives and at Inter Levels of Officers of BEML

Table 13

Mean, S.D. and 't' values of Leadership Perspectives of DGMs and AGMs

S.No.	Leadership Perspectives	DGMs			AGMs			't' value
		Mean	N	S.D.	Mean	N	S.D.	
1	Positive Leadership (S)	80.750	8	7.649	78.125	16	8.936	0.465
2	Negative Leadership (G)	53.125	8	9.463	45.688	16	8.515	0.084

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 13 present mean, S.D. and 't' values of the leadership perspectives of DGMs and AGMs of BEML. Mean values of positive and negative leadership styles are higher in DGMs than AGMs. In positive and negative leadership styles of DGMs and AGMs do not differ significantly as the 't' values

of these styles are less than the critical value (S0.465, $P<0.05$ and G0.084, $P<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis of “there is no significant difference among different leadership perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML” is accepted.

Table 14

Mean, S.D. and 't' values of Leadership Perspectives of AGMs and SMs

S.N o.	Leadership Perspectives	AGMs			SMs			't' value
		Mean	N	S.D.	Mean	N	S.D.	
1	Positive Leadership (S)	78.125	16	8.936	76.417	24	5.160	0.503

2	Negative Leadership (G)	45.688	16	8.515	58.125	24	11.932	0.001
---	-------------------------	--------	----	-------	--------	----	--------	-------

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 14 present mean, S.D. and 't' values of the leadership perspectives of AGMs and SMs of BEML. Mean value of positive leadership style is higher in AGMs than SMs whereas mean value of negative leadership style is higher in SMs than AGMs. In positive and negative leadership styles of

AGMs and SMs do not differ significantly as the 't' values of these styles are less than the critical value (S0.503, $P < 0.05$ and G0.001, $P < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant difference among different leadership perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 15

Mean, S.D. and 't' values of Leadership Perspectives of SMs and Ms

S. No.	Leadership Perspectives	SMs			Managers			't' value
		Mean	N	S.D.	Mean	N	S.D.	
1	Positive Leadership (S)	76.417	24	5.160	77.938	48	7.700	0.344
2	Negative Leadership (G)	58.125	24	11.932	53.042	48	8.686	0.072

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 15 present mean, S.D. and 't' values of the leadership perspectives of SMs and Managers of BEML.

Mean values of negative leadership style is higher in SMs than Managers whereas mean value of positive leadership style is higher in Managers than SMs. In positive and negative

leadership styles of SMs and Managers do not differ significantly as the 't' values of these styles are less than the critical value (S0.344, $P < 0.05$ and G0.072, $P < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant difference among different leadership perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 16

Mean, S.D. and 't' values of Leadership Perspectives of Ms and AMs

S.No.	Leadership Perspectives	Ms			AMs			't' value
		Mean	N	S.D.	Mean	N	S.D.	
1	Positive Leadership (S)	77.938	48	7.700	80.023	88	6.044	0.109
2	Negative Leadership (G)	53.042	48	8.686	54.568	88	9.512	0.346

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 16 present mean, S.D. and 't' values of the leadership perspectives of Managers and AMs of BEML.

Mean values of positive and negative leadership styles are higher in AMs than Managers. In positive and negative leadership styles of Managers and AMs do not differ

significantly as the 't' values of these styles are less than the critical value (S0.109, $P < 0.05$ and G0.346, $P < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis of "there is no significant difference among different leadership perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML" is accepted.

Table 17

Mean, S.D. and 't' values of Leadership Perspectives of AMs and Engineers

S.No.	Leadership Perspectives	Assistant Managers			Engineers			't' value
		Mean	N	S.D.	Mean	N	S.D.	
1	Positive Leadership (S)	80.023	88	6.044	77.186	118	7.716	0.004
2	Negative Leadership (G)	54.568	88	9.512	56.398	118	8.706	0.159

Source: Compiled from field survey

Table 17 present mean, S.D. and 't' values of the leadership perspectives of AMs and Engineers of BEML. Mean values of positive leadership style is higher in AMs than Engineers whereas mean value of negative leadership style is higher in Engineers than Assistant Managers. In positive and negative leadership styles of AMs and Engineers do not differ significantly as the 't' values of these styles are less than the critical value (S0.004, $P < 0.05$ and G0.159, $P < 0.05$). Hence,

the hypothesis of "there is no significant difference among different leadership perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML" is accepted.

5. Conclusions

The following are the conclusions from the above study:

1. Significant relationship of Leadership Perspectives with certain Socio Economic and Organizational

- Position (SEOP) variables of employees in BEML is found in some cases.
2. In most of the cases there is no significant relationship between Leadership Perspectives of employees in BEML and
 3. There is no significant difference between the different Leadership Perspectives in the inter levels of employees in BEML.

Reference

1. Bennis, W. G. "Leadership Theory and Administrative Behaviour: The Problem of Authority," *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol.4, 1959.
2. Henry Fayol, *General and Industrial Management*, Pitman and Sons, London, 1949.
3. George R. Terry, *Principles of Management*, Richard D. Irwin, Inc. Home Wood, Illinois, 1968.
4. Ralph M. Stogdill, "Personal Factors Associated with Leadership: A Survey of the Literature", *Journal of Psychology*, Jan.1948.
5. Lewin, K., Lippitt, R. and White, R.K. "Patterns of Aggressive Behaviour in Experimentally Created 'Social Climates'", *Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol.10, 1939.
6. Robert R. Blake and Jane S. Mouton., *The Managerial Grid*, (Gulf Publishing, Houston, 1978) Kurt Lewin, Ronald Lippitt and Ralph K. White "Patterns of Aggressive Behaviour in Experimentally Created Social Climates", *Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol.10, No.2, May, 1939.